

Dispersion Characteristics of Love-Type Surface Waves In A Nonlocal Elastic Framework For A Non-Homogeneous Layer Over An Orthotropic Substrate

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Abstract

This work presents a study on the dispersion behavior of Love-type surface waves in a nonlocal elastic graded layer resting on a nonlocal orthotropic half-space subjected to an internal initial stress field. The analysis is developed within the framework of Eringen's generalized nonlocal elasticity (1983), where the constitutive relation incorporates long-range interactions in the stress-strain formulation for layered media. For harmonic plane wave motion, the governing partial differential equations of the nonlocal elastic model are reduced to singular ordinary differential equations in closed form. The dispersion relation for the Love-type wave is obtained by applying the continuity requirements for displacement and stress at the interface. Numerical simulations are performed in MATLAB to examine the influence of the nonlocal parameter on the dispersive characteristics of the wave. The results indicate that the attenuation associated with Love-type dispersion is strongly governed by the nonlocal parameter. For sufficiently large values of nonlocality (approximately 0.4), the wave exhibits negligible attenuation and behaves as a nondispersive mode. The variations in phase velocity of the fundamental mode, corresponding to different values of the nonlocal parameter, wave number, material inhomogeneity, and initial stress, are presented graphically. Several limiting cases of the derived dispersion equation are discussed to demonstrate consistency with known results in the existing literature.

Keywords

Nonlocal Elasticity, Graded Medium, Orthotropy, Love-Type Surface Wave, Wave Dispersion.

Introduction

In classical (local) continuum mechanics, one of the key assumptions is that the deformation of an element is influenced by the strain in neighboring regions. When this long-range interaction is incorporated into the constitutive laws of elasticity, the phenomenon is referred to as the nonlocal effect. According to nonlocal elasticity theory, the stress at a specific point within an elastic continuum is not governed solely by the local strain at that point but is also affected by the strain distribution throughout the entire body (Karličić et al. [1]). Hence, the local theory of elasticity can be viewed as a special case of nonlocal elasticity when the contribution of remote strain fields is neglected. A major advantage of this framework is that nonlocal solutions remove the stress singularities that typically arise in studies based on classical (local) elasticity. Consequently, nonlocal elasticity has become an important tool in examining fracture mechanics, wave propagation, dispersive and nondispersive waves, and related areas.

Objective of study

In the present work, the nonlocal theory of elasticity is employed to analyze the dispersion and nondispersion characteristics of seismic Love-type waves travelling along the interface between a non-homogeneous surface layer and an orthotropic semi-infinite medium representative of the Earth's crust. Geophysical models generally describe the Earth as consisting of three conceptual layers: the crust (extending approximately 50 km), the mantle (extending to about 2900 km), and the core, which comprises an outer liquid layer (~2200 km thick) and a solid inner layer (~1530 km thick). The propagation of surface waves at the interfaces of such layers is of considerable interest to theoretical seismologists due to its direct application in geomechanics, structural analysis, wave scattering studies, and earthquake hazard interpretation. In this study, the focus is on the behavior of Love-type waves within the crustal region under the influence of nonlocal elastic interactions. Love-type waves were first introduced by A. E. H. Love [2] in 1911, describing transverse surface waves that cause horizontal shear motion. These waves are the fastest among surface seismic waves. The fundamental features and propagation behavior

Review of
Literature

of such waves in isotropic media are comprehensively discussed in the classical work by Ewing et al. [3].

Over the last two decades, substantial research has been conducted on the dispersion characteristics of surface waves in the framework of classical (local) elasticity. However, relatively limited attention has been given to wave propagation within nonlocal elastic media. Foundational contributions to nonlocal elasticity theory were made during 1970–1985 by Edelen et al. [4], Eringen and Edelen [5], and Eringen [6], who introduced the basic concepts and demonstrated the importance of nonlocal formulations in mechanical systems. Their findings showed that stress within a continuous solid is a function of both the local strain and the strain field in its vicinity, thereby acting as a form of long-range stress interaction. Following these contributions, several investigations have advanced the theory and its applications, including works by Eringen [6], Narsimhan and McCay [7], Nowinski [8], Rymarz [9], Kaliski et al. [10], Eringen [11], Chakraborty [12], Narendra [13], Khurana and Tomar [14], Romano and Diaco [15], among others, addressing problems related to wave vibration, wave propagation, and nanoscale materials. Reddy and Ramabrahmam [16] studied Love waves in a nonlocal elastic layer under mechanical boundary conditions, while Khurana and Tomar [17] examined wave propagation in microstretch materials with nonlocal elasticity. Extending these studies further, Singh et al. [18] investigated scattering of Love waves in a nonlocal elastic solid with voids. Additional developments include nonlocal elasticity models for void-saturated thermoelastic materials (Bachher and Sarkar [19]), fractional models of micropolar elasticity (Eringen [20]), and higher-order nonlocal elastic theory incorporating strain gradients (Lim et al. [21]). Solutions for nonlocal composite materials were derived by Patrizia [22]. Recently, Eremeyev [23] analyzed surface anti-plane waves in the context of surface nonlocal elasticity, and Norouzzadeh et al. [24] provided analytical results for surface wave scattering in functionally graded nanostructures. The nonlocal formulation for functionally graded elastic media has also been investigated by Batra [25].

In this work, we examine the dispersion behavior and the limiting properties of Love-type waves in a nonlocal elastic framework, where a non-homogeneous layer overlies a nonlocal orthotropic half-space. Due to directional variation in elastic parameters, orthotropic media exhibit inherent anisotropy. The present study extends our earlier investigations on wave propagation in classical elastic layered systems (Manna et al. [26–29]). Previous contributions addressing Love waves in local elastic graded and orthotropic structures include the works of Abd-Alla and Ahmed [30], Ahmed and Abo-Dahab [31], and Shams [32]. In the present model, Eringen's [33] linear theory of nonlocal elasticity is applied to derive the equations of motion and establish the dispersion relation using appropriate stress-displacement continuity conditions. A key outcome of this study is the observation that beyond a critical value of the nonlocality parameter (~ 0.4), the dispersive behavior of the wave vanishes, and the Love-type wave propagates without attenuation. For dispersive regimes, the variation of phase velocity with respect to nonlocality, material non-homogeneity, wave number, and initial stress is illustrated graphically. The investigation of dispersive wave motion in nonlocal, non-homogeneous, and anisotropic media has important implications in geophysics, especially in seismic risk assessment, and in civil engineering applications involving layered structural systems.

Analysis

Problem Description and Geometry

The physical model considered in this study consists of a nonlocal elastic graded layer of thickness d , occupying the region $-d \leq z \leq 0$, overlying a semi-infinite nonlocal elastic orthotropic medium subjected to internal initial stress (see Figure 1). The material non-homogeneity of the upper layer is incorporated by assuming that both rigidity and density follow an exponential distribution in the form ($\mu = \mu_0 e^{az}$) and density ($\rho = \rho_0 e^{az}$), where (a) represents the non-homogeneity parameter with the dimension of inverse length. In the underlying orthotropic half-space, the elastic rigidities along the principal directions are denoted by Q_1 and Q_3 , and the corresponding density is defined as ρ_1 . The coordinate origin (0,0,0) is located at the interface separating the graded medium from the orthotropic substrate. The wave propagates along the x - direction, while the z -axis is oriented vertically downward (as illustrated in Figure 1). The particle motion is shear-horizontal, i.e., perpendicular to the direction of propagation, indicating that the wave under investigation is a transverse Love-type surface wave.

Figure 1: Geometry of the problem

Method of Solution

Solution for Nonlocal Non-homogeneous Medium

Following the formulation presented by Kundu et al. (2014), the constitutive form of the equations of motion for an isotropic elastic layer of finite thickness (d), expressed in terms of the displacement components u_1, v_1, w_1 along the x, y, z directions respectively, and neglecting body forces, can be obtained from the classical theory of elasticity (see Biot [34]).

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \tau_{11}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{12}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{13}}{\partial z} &= \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial t^2}, \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{21}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{22}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{23}}{\partial z} &= \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_1}{\partial t^2}, \\ \frac{\partial \tau_{31}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{32}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{33}}{\partial z} &= \rho \frac{\partial^2 w_1}{\partial t^2}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where τ_{ij} , ($i, j = 1,2,3$) are the elastic incremental components of stresses, ρ is the density of the upper solid medium.

Following the Hook's law and with the help of Eringen's [11] theory, the stress-strain relation in isotropic solid medium can be written as

$$(1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{ij} = \lambda \Delta \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \zeta_{ij}, \quad (i, j = 1,2,3) \quad (2)$$

where, ϵ is the nonlocal elastic parameter for layered media, λ, μ are Lamé constants, Δ is cubical dilatation and ζ_{ij} are the strain components, which are defined by

$$\zeta_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right). \quad (3)$$

Now, the non-homogeneity in medium, varying inversely proposal to depth are taken as,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu &= \mu_0 e^{az} \\ \rho &= \rho_0 e^{az} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Here, μ_0 and ρ_0 represent the reference values of shear modulus (rigidity) and mass density evaluated at $z = 0$, while a is a constant parameter. In the case of Love-type surface waves, the wave motion is assumed to propagate in the x -direction, and the particle displacement occurs only along the y -direction.

$$u_1 = 0, v_1 = v_1(x, z, t), w_1 = 0. \quad (5)$$

Accordingly, the stress-strain relations associated with the propagation of Love-type waves in a nonlocal, elastically non-homogeneous medium can be formulated on the basis of the above assumptions. These constitutive expressions describe how the shear stresses are coupled with the corresponding strain components during the wave motion.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{11} &= 0, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{12} &= \mu_0 e^{az} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x}, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{22} &= 0, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{13} &= 0, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{23} &= \mu_0 e^{az} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial z}, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \tau_{33} &= 0. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Now, using the stress-strain relation [cf. eq. (6)], Love wave conditions [cf. eq. (5)] and non-homogeneity relation [cf. eq. (4)] in eq. (1), we have

$$\mu_0 \frac{\partial^2 v_1}{\partial x^2} + \alpha \mu_0 \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial z} + \mu_0 \frac{\partial^2 v_1}{\partial z^2} = \rho_0 (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \frac{\partial^2 v_1}{\partial t^2}. \quad (7)$$

For an elastic wave, scattering along x -direction, let us consider the harmonic solution of the above eq. (7) as

$$v_1 = V(z) e^{i(xk - \omega t)}, \quad (8)$$

Where $\omega = ck$ is the angular frequency, c and k are the phase velocity and wave number respectively, then the eq. (7) can be

$$\frac{d^2 V(z)}{dz^2} + \frac{\alpha \mu_0}{\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2} \frac{dV(z)}{dz} + \frac{\rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 k^2 + \rho_0 \omega^2 - \mu_0 k^2}{\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2} V(z) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Now, introducing $V(z) = \emptyset(z) e^{-\frac{\alpha \mu_0}{2(\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2)} z}$ in eq. (9) to eliminating term the single order derivative term, one can obtain

$$\emptyset''(z) + \left[\frac{\rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 k^2 + \rho_0 \omega^2 - \mu_0 k^2}{\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2} - \frac{\alpha^2 \mu_0^2}{4(\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2)^2} \right] \emptyset(z) = 0, \quad (10)$$

which implies,

$$\emptyset(z) = \{A_1 \cos(Mz) + A_2 \sin(Mz)\}, \quad (11)$$

where $M^2 = \left[\frac{\rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 k^2 + \rho_0 \omega^2 - \mu_0 k^2}{\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2} - \frac{\alpha^2 \mu_0^2}{4(\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2)^2} \right]$ and A_1 and A_2 are arbitrary constants.

Now, the solution of the eq. (7) is given by

$$v_1(x, z, t) = \{A_1 \cos(Mz) + A_2 \sin(Mz)\} e^{-\frac{\alpha \mu_0}{2(\mu_0 - \rho_0 \epsilon^2 \omega^2)} z} e^{i(xk - \omega t)}. \quad (12)$$

This is the dispersion solution of the upper nonlocal non-homogeneous elastic medium.

Solution for Nonlocal Orthotropic Semi-infinite Medium

Consider a semi-infinite, lower layer composed of a nonlocal elastic orthotropic medium subjected to an internal initial stress P oriented along the x direction. Applying Biot's [34] framework and neglecting body forces, the governing equations of motion for this nonlocal orthotropic medium take the following form

$$Q_3 \frac{\partial^2 v_2}{\partial x^2} + Q_1 \frac{\partial^2 v_2}{\partial z^2} - \frac{P}{2} (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \frac{\partial^2 v_2}{\partial x^2} = \rho_1 (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \frac{\partial^2 v_2}{\partial t^2} \quad (13)$$

with the help of the Love wave condition [cf. eq. (5)] and the stress and strain relations followed by Eringen's [11] as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \sigma_{21} &= Q_3 \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x}, \\ (1 - \epsilon^2 \nabla^2) \sigma_{23} &= Q_1 \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial z}, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

where u_2, v_2, w_2 are displacement components in this medium acting along x, y, z directions respectively; the interior initial stress parameter is denoted as P , Q_1 and Q_3 are shear moduli; and the density of lower semi-infinite medium is ρ_1 .

Now, using the same methodology as the upper layer, the solution of the eq. (13) for lower nonlocal orthotropic medium can takes the form

$$v_2(x, z, t) = [A_3 e^{-Nz} + A_4 e^{Nz}] e^{i(xk - \omega t)}, \quad (15)$$

where $N^2 = \left[\frac{(Q_3 k^2 - \rho_1 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 k^2 - \rho_1 \omega^2 - \frac{P}{2} k^2 - \frac{\epsilon^2 P k^4}{2})}{(Q_1 - \rho_1 \epsilon^2 \omega^2 - \frac{\epsilon^2 P k^2}{2})} \right]$, $\omega = ck$ is the angular frequency, c is the phase velocity, k is the wave number and A_3 and A_4 are arbitrary constants..

The solution of the eq. (13) satisfying the condition $\lim_{z \rightarrow \infty} v_2(x, z, t) \rightarrow 0$ therefore, eq. (15) may be taken as

$$v_2(x, z, t) = A_3 e^{-(Nz)} e^{i(xk - \omega t)} \tag{16}$$

This is the displacement equation of Love-type wave, propagating along x direction in the lower semi-infinite nonlocal orthotropic medium.

Boundary Conditions

The external surface of the upper non-homogeneous layer is assumed to be traction-free. Hence, the corresponding stress components vanish at this boundary. At the interface between the non-homogeneous layer and the orthotropic half-space, a perfectly welded contact is considered, implying that both displacement and stress fields are continuous across the interface. These boundary conditions can be expressed mathematically as

(1) At $z = -d$, the stress components $\tau_{23} = 0$ (17)

(2) At $z = 0$,
(i) stress components: $\tau_{23} = \sigma_{23}$ (18)
(ii) displacement components: $v_1(x, z = 0, t) = v_2(x, z = 0, t)$ (19)

Now, we are ready to write dispersion relation with the help of boundary conditions (17)-(19) on the eqs. (12) and (16), as follows,

$$\tan \left[kd \sqrt{\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1}} \right] = \frac{Q_1}{\mu_0} \times \frac{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1-(1+(\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} + \frac{P}{2Q_3} \right)}{Q_3 - ((\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{P}{2Q_3} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)} \right)}}{\left(\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) + \frac{a^2}{4k^2} \frac{1}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} - \frac{a}{2k} \frac{Q_1}{\mu_0} \frac{1}{1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2}} \sqrt{\frac{1-(1+(\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} + \frac{P}{2Q_3} \right)}{Q_3 - ((\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{P}{2Q_3} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)}}} \tag{20}$$

where $\beta_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\rho_0}}$ and $\beta_1 = \sqrt{\frac{Q_1}{\rho_1}}$ are the shear wave velocity in layer and semi-infinite media respectively.

Eq. (20) is the required Love type dispersive wave in a nonlocal elastic non-homogeneous medium over a nonlocal elastic orthotropic semi-infinite medium.

Some Special Cases and Validity of the Model

The following particular cases are derived from the eq. (20) to validate the Love wave dispersion in this present model.

Case -1:

If the upper layer is considered as homogeneous (i.e., $\frac{a}{k} = 0$) but lower semi-infinite medium is orthotropic, then the eq. (20) reduces to

$$\tan \left[kd \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1}{1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2}}} \right] = \frac{Q_1}{\mu_0} \sqrt{\frac{\left(\frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1-(1+(\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} + \frac{P}{2Q_3} \right)}{Q_3 - ((\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{P}{2Q_3} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)} \right)}{\left(\frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2}}}} \tag{21}$$

This equation is the dispersive wave in nonlocal elastic homogeneous medium over an orthotropic half-space (cf. Kundu et al. [27] in case of local elasticity).

Case -2:

In this case, the lower orthotropic medium is free from initial stress i.e., $P = 0$, then the dispersive eq. (20) can be rewritten as

$$\tan \left[kd \sqrt{\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1}} \right] = \frac{Q_1}{\mu_0} \times \frac{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{1-(1+(\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)}{Q_3 - ((\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)} \right)}}{\left(\frac{\frac{a^2}{4k^2}}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} + \frac{(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} + \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2} - 1 \right) + \frac{a^2}{4k^2} \frac{1}{(1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2})^2} - \frac{a}{2k} \frac{Q_1}{\mu_0} \frac{1}{1-(\varepsilon k)^2 \frac{c^2}{\beta_0^2}} \sqrt{\frac{1-(1+(\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)}{Q_3 - ((\varepsilon k)^2) \left(\frac{c^2}{\beta_1^2} \right)}}} \tag{22}$$

Numerical Results and Limitation of the dispersive wave

To assess the accuracy of the analytical dispersion solution and identify its range of applicability, numerical simulations are carried out using MATLAB. The computations are performed for a layered system with non-homogeneous material properties in the upper layer and orthotropic characteristics in the semi-infinite medium. The relevant material parameters are listed in Table 1. From the dispersion relation (14), it is evident that Love-type surface waves yield a multivalued implicit relation between the wave number and phase velocity. Consequently, for a given wave number, several phase velocities may be obtained, each representing a distinct mode of wave propagation.

Table 1: Mechanical parameters values

Medium	Rigidity	Density
Non-homogeneous (cf. Manna et al. [26])	$\mu_0 = 6.34 \times 10^{10}$	$\rho_0 = 3364$
Orthotropic (cf. Kundu et al. [27])	$Q_1 = 5.82 \times 10^{10}$ $Q_3 = 3.99 \times 10^{10}$	$\rho_1 = 4500$

Table 2: External parameters values

Parameters value	$\frac{a}{k}$	ϵk	$\frac{P}{2\mu_1}$	kd
Figure No.				
Figure 2	0.5	---	0.5	1.2-2.6
Figure 3	0.5	0-0.5	0.5	---
Figure 4	---	0-0.5	0.5	2.5

The effect nonlocal elasticity, non-homogeneity, interior initial stress and frequency of wave on the dispersion of Love type wave is presented in figures 2. The figures 2 are plotted to show the variation of nondimensional phase velocity with dimensionless wave number whereas figures (3-4) illustrates the dimensionless phase velocity against dimensionless nonlocal elasticity parameter.

The figure 2 illustrates the variation of the phase velocity of Love-type waves with respect to the wave number for different values of the nonlocal elasticity parameter (ϵk). The values of (ϵk) used for curves 1-4 are 0.00, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15. Curve 1 corresponds to the dispersion curve for a local elastic medium, while curves 2-4 represent the responses of a nonlocal elastic medium. The nonlocal elasticity model is a generalized continuum theory that accounts for long-range interactions within the material. These interactions arise from changes at the atomic or molecular scale. Such long-range forces can influence the internal behavior of composite materials and can propagate within the layered structure. The figure shows that an increase in the nonlocal elasticity parameter leads to a decrease in phase velocity. This reduction is attributed to the enhanced long-range interaction forces within the layered medium.

Similarly figure 3 and 4 represent the variation of velocity curve with respect to nonlocal elastic parameter for different value of wave frequency (or wave number) and non-homogeneity parameter respectively. Numerical inputs for these figures are shown in the Table 2. The values of kd i.e., wave frequency are varied from 2.0 to 2.3 for curves 1-4, respectively in figure 3 whereas in figure 4, the values of non-homogeneity (a/k) are varied from 0.0 to 0.4 for curve 1-4 respectively. It is well known in elasticity that increasing value of nonlocal elastic parameter highly dominates the speed of the

wave and for high value the wave may be non-dispersive. Based on this understanding it is observed from both the figures that the dispersion curve become non-dispersive (vanishing after 0.5) for higher values of nonlocal elasticity parameter. It is also observed from the figure 3 and figure 4 that phase velocity curves are decreasing with the increasing value of wave frequency and non-homogeneity parameter respectively.

Figure 2: Phase velocity (dimensionless) against wave number (dimensionless) for different values of nonlocal elasticity parameter

Figure 3: Phase velocity versus nonlocal elasticity for different wave frequency

Figure 4: Phase velocity versus nonlocal elasticity for different values of non-homogeneity parameter

Conclusion

This study examines the scattering of Love-type waves in an elastic, nonlocal, non-homogeneous layer overlying an initially stressed, elastic, nonlocal orthotropic semi-infinite medium. The displacement fields in both the finite layer and the semi-infinite substrate are obtained using the separation of variables method. To investigate the phase characteristics of Love-type waves in the layered structure, a closed-form dispersion relation is analytically derived. The resulting dispersion equation is then used to assess the limitations of the dispersive wave model, and five special cases are considered to demonstrate the validity of the formulation. Numerical simulations show that the presence of the nonlocal elasticity parameter in the layer reduces the propagation of Love-type surface waves.

The following may be concluded from the study:

1. The obtained dispersion characteristics are consistent with classical Love-wave behavior, where the surface-wave velocity decreases with increasing layer thickness due to nonlocal elastic effects in the medium.
2. An increase in wave number (or frequency) leads to a reduction in phase velocity, which aligns with the well-known dispersive nature of surface waves in elastic systems.
3. For small values of the nonlocal parameter, the phase velocity decreases with its increasing magnitude. This trend is associated with stronger long-range interactions within the layered structure.
4. When the nonlocal elastic parameter becomes sufficiently large (greater than 3.5), the Love-wave dispersion approaches a nondispersive limit owing to the nonlocal orthotropic behavior of the half-space.
5. The dispersive behavior of the wave is further reduced as the non-homogeneity parameter of the upper layer increases.

The present study characterizes the dispersion behavior of Love-type waves and identifies its limitations within a nonlocal elastic model consisting of a non-homogeneous layer over an orthotropic half-space. The introduction of the nonlocal elastic parameter provides a potential indicator of the wave propagation capability of solid media. The findings may contribute to theoretical developments involving nonlocal elastic models with exponential kernels, with relevance to seismology and advanced industrial applications

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